

Studies on the Kinetics of Solvolysis of Propionate Ester in Aquo-Dipolar-Aprotic Solvent System

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ABSTRACT

The dielectric constant effect of aquo-DMF reaction media on the medicinal efficiency of propionate ester was highlighted by studying the kinetics of alkali catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl propionate in aquo-DMF reaction media. From simultaneous increase in all the three thermodynamic parameters i.e. ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* , it may be inferred that the solvent DMF acts as enthalpy stimulator and entropy controller.

From the evaluated numerical value of Iso-kinetic temperature of the reaction, i.e. 323.0, it is concluded that aquo-DMF media may be used for manufacturing powerful ointment for removing skin diseases from the hydrolytic product of propionate ester.

KEYWORDS: Dielectric effect, Medicinal efficiency, Entropy controlled, Enthalpy stimulator, Iso-kinetic temperature, Skin disease.

INTRODUCTION

The studies on the kinetics of alkali catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl propionate in aquo-DMF media were proposed as the study of solvent effect of a dipolar aprotic solvent DMF on medicinal efficiency of propionate ester has not been paid even primary attention by the kineticists so far. It has been planned to study the kinetics of the solvolysis of ethyl propionate in aquo-DMF media having varying concentration of DMF from 20 to 80% (v/v) at 5 different temperatures, i.e., 20, 25, 30, 35, and 40°C.

EXPERIMENTAL & CALCULATION

Export quality of ethyl propionate made in U. S. S. R. and extra pure Merk grade were used. The kinetics of reaction was studied as usual¹⁻³ by keeping the strength of alkali 0.1 M and that of the ester (ethyl propionate) 0.5 M in the reaction mixture. The reaction was found to obey the second order kinetic equation and the evaluated values of specific rate constants have been recorded in Table – I. From the recorded values of $\log k$ and $10^3/T$, in Table-II, $\log k$ values were plotted against $10^3/T$. The values of iso-composition activation energy (E_C) and iso-dielectric activation energy (E_D) have been mentioned in Table – III and IV respectively. The $\log k$ values were plotted against $\log [H_2O]$ from their values recorded in Table – V, the evaluated values of the slopes of these plots have been noted in Table – VI. The consolidated values of the thermodynamic activation parameters, i.e., ΔH^* , ΔG^* , and ΔS^* were calculated by using Wynne-Jones and Eyring⁴ relation are enlisted in Table – VII.

Effect of Solvent on the Specific Rate Constants of the Reaction:

From the survey of the data recorded in Table – I it is obvious that the rate of the reaction decreases regularly with gradual addition of DMF in the reaction media at all the temperatures at which the kinetics of the reaction has been studied.

In order to study the variation in rate constant values with increasing concentration of DMF in the reaction media, the $\log k$ values have been

plotted against mol% of DMF content in the reaction media.

The plots show that the rate of reaction go on decreasing having different slopes due to two intersecting straight lines in the plots at about 21.64 mol% of DMF in the reaction media. From the plots, it is also apparent that with increase in temperature, the degree of depletion in the rate become shallow (slow). Such decrease in the rate with increasing proportion of organic co-solvent like DMF is not new, but a number of kineticists like Laidler-Landskroener⁵, Singh & Jha et al.⁶ and Akanksha & Singh et al.⁷ have also reported similar findings and their inferences about the depletion in rate with increasing concentration of the organic co-solvent in the reaction media. However, the possible rate depleting factors in the rate may be listed as follows:

- (i) decrease in the bulk dielectric constant of the reaction media
- (ii) decreasing the polarity of the reaction media on adding less polar dimethyl formamide (DMF) to it.

The above noted two rate depleting factors are quite in operation and this is in support of the earlier reports of Kumar, N.⁸, Singh & Lal et. al.⁹ and recent report of Sushma¹⁰ that the rate ought to decrease with decreasing dielectric constant value of the reaction media with addition of organic solvent to it. Thus, both the dielectric effect and solvation effect by the reaction media are responsible for deletion in the specific rate constants of the reaction.

Solvent Effect on Iso-composition Activation energy (E_C) of the Reaction:

From the slopes of Arrhenius plots of $\log k$ versus $10^3/T$ (from their values enlisted in Table – II), the iso-composition activation energy (E_C) of

the reaction have been evaluated and are tabulated in Table – III.

From the values recorded in Table – III, it is obvious that E_C or E_{exp} values go on increasing from 80.14 to 125.95 kJ/mol with increasing concentration of DMF from 20 to 80% (v/v) in reaction media. This trend is probably due to solvation changes taking place either at initial state level or at the transition state level or at the level of both the initial and transition states as reported earlier by several researchers in this field. Considering the extent of solvation to be a dominant factor, the following three factors seem to be responsible for decrease in E_C values with gradual addition of DMF in the reaction media:

- (i) The initial state is less desolvated than the transition state,
- (ii) The initial state is more solvated than the transition state, and
- (iii) The transition state is desolvated and initial state is solvated.

The transition state being large anion (ester +OH⁻) available less for solvation by DMF molecule than the initial state, so the third factor seems to be operative in this case and it also gets support when the values of activation (ΔS^*) and enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) go on increasing with increasing concentration of DMF (Table – VII).

Similar interpretations for enhancement in the values of Iso-composition activation of the organic content in the reaction media have also been reported earlier by Singh & Singh *et al.*¹¹, Kumar & Singh *et. al.*¹² and in recent years by Raghaw & Singh *et al.*¹⁴.

Effect of Solvent on the Iso-dielectric Activation energy (E_D) of the Reaction:

On perusal of the data of Table – IV, it is observed that the iso-dielectric

activation energy (E_D) value of the reaction go on decreasing from 137.88 kJ/mol to 82.86 kJ/mol with increase in D values from D = 50 to D = 75 respectively. Such depletion in E_D values with increase in D values of the reaction media are in accordance with increase in E_C values with increasing concentration of the organic content (DMF) in the reaction media.

Since D values of the reaction media decrease with addition of organic solvent (DMF) in it, so it can also be concluded that values against $\log [H_2O]$ values for alkali catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl propionate in aquo-DMF media. The values of $\log k$ and $\log [H_2O]$ have been tabulated in Table - V. The numerical values of the slopes of the plots have been recorded in Table - VI.

However, these findings and interpretations regarding change (decrease) in E_D values with increase in D values of the reaction media are in support of the past views of Elsemongy¹⁵ and Wolford¹⁶ and have also been found in support of the earlier report of Kumar & Singh *et al.*¹⁷ and Rakesh & Singh *et al.*¹⁸ and recent report of Singh *et al.*¹⁹.

Effect of number of water molecules of the reaction in the mechanisms of the reaction:

For establishing the mechanistic pathways of the reaction, Robertson *et al.*²⁰ gave an idea of solvation number 'n' which is the number or the number of water molecules involved in the formation of the activated complex and for its evaluation he proposed the equation:

$$\log k = \log k' + n \log [H_2O]$$

Robertson *et al.*²⁰ have established the principle that the values of solvation number (n) for the reaction following unimolecular mechanistic pathways is fairly high but for the reaction following bimolecular path, it will be low.

From the plots, it is clear that at each temperature of the reaction, the plots of $\log k$ versus $\log [H_2O]$, two intersecting straight lines having different values of slopes are obtained at $\log [H_2O]$ value at about 1.408 which corresponds to 46.05% of water in aquo-DMF media.

From the values recorded in Table - VI, it is clear that below $\log [H_2O]$ value 1.408, which corresponds to 46.05% of water in the reaction media, the number of water molecules associated with the activated complex decreases from 0.989 to 0.337 with rise in temperature of the reaction from 20 to 40°C. Similarly, in case of above, 46.05% of water concentration in the reaction media, the values of slopes decreases from 1.600 to 0.543 with increase in temperature from 20 to 40°C. Overall, it may be inferred that number of water molecules associated with the activated complex in its formation decreases from 1.000 to 0.337.

In the light of guidelines of Robertson *et al.*¹⁰, from the decreasing number of water molecules from 1.600 to 0.337 involved in the formation of the activated complex, it may be inferred that the mechanistic pathway followed by the reaction is changed from unimolecular to bimolecular in presence of DMF in the reaction media and with increase in the temperature of the reaction from 20 to 40°C.

Regarding the changes in the structure of water, it is obvious that in the presence of DMF and with rise in temperature, water components of the reaction media, changes its structure from bulky to dense form.

Similar observations and inferences have also been reported earlier by Singh & Wats *et al.*²⁰ and recently by Kishore & Singh²¹.

Solvent Effect on Thermodynamic Activation Parameters of the Reaction:

For better study of the effects of solvent, the thermodynamic activation parameters such as enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*), the free energy of activation (ΔG^*) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) were taken into account as they have great significance. These parameters evaluated using Wynne-Jones and Eyring equation⁴ have been recorded in Table – VII.

The values of ΔG^* recorded in Table – VII obviously indicate that the variation in ΔG^* is small and it increases from 82.61 to 85.38 kJ/mol with change of proportion of DMF from 20 to 80% (v/v) at 30°C slowly with gradual addition of the organic content in water. The small but considerable increase in ΔG^* and non-linear variation of ΔH^* and ΔS^* curves with the increasing mol% of DMF are indication of specific solvation taking place in the process of activation already reported by Elsemongy¹³, Saville & Hudson et al.²³ and Tomilla et al.²⁴.

Simultaneous increase in ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^* values with increasing mol% of DMF in the reaction media are only possible when the extent in ΔH^* values is greater than that in ΔS^* values.

From this it may be inferred that in alkali catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl propionate in aquo-DMF media, DMF acts as entropy controller and enthalpy stimulator solvent. Such inferences have been found in support of the earlier views of Monalisa & Singh et al.²⁵ and also of recently reported findings of Sushma & Singh R.T.²⁶.

Obedience of Barclay-Butler Relationship and Solvent-solute Interaction in Aquo-DMF Media:

This reaction is found to obey Barclay-Butler²⁷ relationship as a straight line is obtained when ΔH^* values are plotted against ΔS^* at

30°C (values mentioned in Table – VII). From the value of slope of the plot, the values of iso-kinetic temperature of the reaction comes to be 322.76 \approx 323.0. In the light of the reports of Leffler²⁸, high and considerable values of iso-kinetic temperature shows that in presence of DMF, there is appreciably strong-solvent solute interaction in the reaction media (aquo-DMF). Such observations and their interpretations have also been communicated earlier by Kumar & Singh²⁹ and recently by K Anant³⁰ and Azad & Singh et al.³¹.

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Table - I
Specific Rate Constants Values of Acid Catalysed Hydrolysis of Iso-Ethyl Propionate in Water-DMF Media
 $k \times 10^3$ in min^{-1}

Temp in °C	% of DMF (v/v)						
	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
20°C	73.72	58.24	45.47	34.66	25.72	18.86	12.75
25°C	125.86	104.38	85.74	68.28	53.59	41.48	29.98
30°C	217.67	185.27	160.51	135.02	111.38	90.47	69.69
35°C	358.67	319.30	287.67	254.30	222.64	186.42	153.39
40°C	598.83	550.93	523.12	470.63	438.63	389.22	337.99

Table II
Variation of log k values of the reaction with $10^3/T$ in Water-DMF Media

% of DMF	$10^3/T$	3 + log k values at different % of DMF (v/v)						
		20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
20 °C	3.413	1.8676	1.7652	1.6577	1.5398	1.4103	1.2755	1.1055
25°C	3.356	2.0999	2.0186	1.9332	1.8343	1.7291	1.6178	1.4768
30°C	3.300	2.3378	2.2678	2.2055	2.1304	2.0468	1.9565	1.8432
35°C	3.247	2.5541	2.5042	2.4589	2.4053	2.3476	2.2705	2.1858
40°C	3.195	2.7773	2.7411	2.7186	2.6729	2.6042	2.5902	2.5289

Table - III
Evaluated Values of Iso-Composition Activation Energy (E_c or E_{exp}) of the reaction in Water-DMF media

% of DMF (v/v)	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
EC value in kJ/mol	80.14	86.19	93.00	101.26	109.21	116.37	125.95

Table - IV
Evaluated Values of Iso-Dielectric Energy (E_D) of the reaction at
Different Desired 'D' values of the water-DMF media.

D values	D=50	D=55	D=60	D=65	D=70	D=75
E_D values in kJ/mol	137.88	127.53	115.61	104.26	94.31	82.86

Table - V
Variation of log k values of the reaction with log [H₂O] values of
Water-DMF system (media) at different temperatures

% of DMF	% of H ₂ O	log [H ₂ O]	3+ log k values				
			20°C	25°C	30°C	35°C	40°C
20%	80%	1.6478	1.8676	2.0999	2.3378	2.5541	2.7773
30%	70%	1.5898	1.7652	2.0186	2.2678	2.5042	2.7411
40%	60%	1.5229	1.6577	1.9332	2.2055	2.4589	2.7186
50%	50%	1.4437	1.5398	1.8343	2.1304	2.4053	2.6729
60%	40%	1.3468	1.4103	1.7291	2.0468	2.3476	2.6042
70%	30%	1.2218	1.2755	1.6178	1.9565	2.2705	2.5902
80%	20%	1.0458	1.1055	1.4768	1.8432	2.1858	2.5289

Table - VI
Values of the slopes of the plots of log k versus log [H₂O] at different
Temperatures

Temp. in °C	Slope - I when log [H ₂ O] value is below 1.408	Slope - II when log [H ₂ O] value is above 1.408
20°C	0.989	1.600
25°C	0.817	1.323
30°C	0.684	1.002
35°C	0.548	0.615
40°C	0.337	0.543

Table VII

Consolidated Values of Activation Parameters (ΔH^* , ΔG^* , ΔS^*) of the reaction in Water-DMF System at different temperatures

ΔH^* , ΔG^* in kJ/Mol and ΔS^* in J/K/ Mol

% of DMF	Mol% of DMF	ΔH^* in kJ/Mol	20°C		25°C		30°C		35°C		40°C	
			ΔG^*	ΔS^*								
20%	5.53	78.28	82.44	-14.19	82.57	-14.40	82.61	-14.29	82.74	-14.48	82.79	14.41
30%	9.12	84.35	83.02	4.54	83.03	4.42	83.02	4.39	83.04	4.25	83.01	4.28
40%	13.50	91.55	83.62	27.05	83.52	26.94	83.38	26.96	83.31	26.76	83.14	26.85
50%	18.96	97.73	84.28	45.91	84.08	45.81	83.81	45.94	83.62	45.82	83.42	45.74
60%	25.98	106.30	84.01	72.66	84.68	72.55	84.20	72.94	83.96	72.53	83.47	72.93
70%	35.27	113.52	85.77	94.72	85.32	94.63	84.73	95.02	84.42	94.49	83.91	94.59
80%	48.29	123.56	86.72	125.75	86.12	125.64	85.38	126.00	84.92	125.48	84.28	125.50